

EFFECTIVENESS OF GOVERNMENT PUBLIC RELATIONS STRATEGIES IN SHAPING PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS OF TARABA STATE'S FREE EDUCATION POLICY

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Abstract

This study investigated the Government Public Relations (GPR) strategies employed by the Taraba State Government to promote its 2023 free education policy. It examined levels of public awareness, perceptions of the policy, and the systemic challenges undermining these GPR efforts. The research adopted a mixed-methods design, utilising a quantitative descriptive survey of 384 members of the public and qualitative in-depth interviews with 26 strategic stakeholders, including school administrators, traditional leaders, and information officers. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and thematic analysis. Findings revealed that the primary PR strategy employed by the government was media relations. This approach achieved a high level of policy awareness (Grand Mean = 3.42), but failed to foster deep understanding, favourable perception, or policy acceptance. The public largely perceived the initiative as a political gimmick. The major challenge undermining the GPR efforts was the lack of two-way communication between the government and the citizenry, resulting in a significant feedback gap due to over-reliance on traditional one-way media. The study recommends the adoption of a two-way symmetrical model that decentralises communication through localised committees, digital transparency trackers, and direct interpersonal engagement with traditional institutions.

Introduction

Public Relations (PR) is widely recognised as a key factor in the success of any institution, including government. In contemporary governance, the success of social interventions depends less on technical merit and more on the quality of the relationship between the state and its constituents (Koeswayo et al., 2024). Government Public Relations (GPR) serves as a strategic management function designed to foster mutual understanding and cooperation (Mbaana & Santas, 2024). Rooted in democratic principles, GPR ensures institutional legitimacy through transparency and two-way communication, acting as a vital intermediary to prevent public resistance arising from misinformation or perceived communicative neglect (Princewell & Okoye, 2015).

In Nigeria, public policy implementation is hampered by a significant trust deficit. Historical issues of corruption and poor accountability have left many citizens expressing a lack of confidence in leadership (Ahmad, 2025). For instance, the Africa Polling Institute's 2025 Social Cohesion Report and the Edelman Trust Barometer reveal that trust in government has fallen to historic lows, with over 83 per cent of Nigerians expressing little or no confidence in government (Leadership News, 2024).

The lack of trust in government has implications for citizens' cooperation and participation in public policies and programmes. Beesley and Hawkins (2022, in Adaba & Boio, 2024) assert that when citizens lack trust in government and its institutions, the outcome can be detrimental to the effective implementation of public policies. It is on this premise that whenever a policy is introduced, especially at federal and state levels, governments often deploy diverse public relations strategies to create awareness, disseminate information, and encourage citizens' support and participation.

In Taraba State, the government introduced a free education policy in July 2023, offering tuition-free primary and secondary education alongside a 50 per cent reduction in tertiary fees (Gai, 2025). Since its inception, the government has utilised various relational and communication strategies to promote the policy and encourage uptake. However, the policy has generated significant public debate across the state. While some have lauded the initiative, others argue that it is merely a political gimmick. Although existing studies have examined the implementation of the policy, there is a lack of empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of the Government Public Relations strategies employed. This study addresses that gap by evaluating the specific PR mechanisms utilised and their impact on public perception of the free education policy.

Statement of the Problem

The success of public policy is fundamentally dependent on public support, which often falters due to negative perception or trust deficits (Campbell, 2023). In Taraba State, the Free Education Policy is a landmark initiative designed to alleviate financial burdens and increase enrolment; however, it has been met with significant scepticism. Many citizens perceive the policy as a political gimmick, citing dilapidated infrastructure and inadequate instructional materials as evidence of a disconnect between government claims and reality (Gai, 2025). This suggests a critical gap between the Government Public Relations (GPR) strategies deployed and the actual public perception of the free education policy. Although existing literature has extensively examined public relations and governance issues in several states of Nigeria such as Kogi and Imo (Omachi et al., 2025; Anyijuka, 2025; Ahmed et al., 2024). However, there is a conspicuous dearth of research specifically addressing Taraba State's educational reforms.

Studies conducted in other states such as Kogi or Imo cannot be readily generalised to Taraba due to its distinct socio-political landscape, characterised by unique ethnic diversity, complex traditional governance structures, and differing levels of political stability and public trust in government institutions. Existing studies typically address national crises or corporate PR, leaving a localised empirical void. This research is necessary to bridge that gap by determining whether the government's PR efforts effectively foster policy acceptance, as failure to align institutional intent with public perception could lead to the ultimate collapse of this vital reform.

Research Questions

Based on the research objectives, the following research questions are formulated:

1. What specific public relations strategies has the Taraba State Government employed to communicate the free education policy to the public?
2. What is the level of public awareness and understanding of the free education policy among citizens in Taraba State?
3. How do citizens perceive the Taraba State free education policy in relation to the government's public relations efforts?

4. What are the key challenges undermining public acceptance of government PR messages regarding the free education policy in Taraba State?

Literature Review

The practice of public relations (PR) within government institutions is characterized by a global tension between its strategic potential and operational underdevelopment. Internationally, research highlights significant structural barriers; Geremew (2017) found that PR in Ethiopian municipalities was hindered by a lack of strategic role clarity, while Anyijuka (2016) noted that Ugandan agencies often lack established units and evaluative data despite the utility of PR in policy promotion. In contrast, studies from Kenya (Kaleli et al., 2021) and Indonesia (Niswaty et al., 2023; Kede et al., 2021) demonstrate that structured PR tools ranging from community relations to hybrid digital-conventional channels significantly enhance public sensitization and transparency, particularly during crises. However, digital implementation remains inconsistent; Irawanto et al. (2022) identified that budget constraints and limited technical skills often neutralize the benefits of social media engagement.

In the Nigerian context, the literature reveals a disconnect between the deployment of PR strategies and their ultimate impact on public behavior. Eyo and Onyewuchi (2025) observe that public institutions still rely heavily on the antiquated Press Agency/Publicity model, characterized by one-way, hierarchical communication. This lack of depth is echoed by Ahmed et al. (2024), who found that while the Ministry of Education utilizes diverse tools like media relations and sponsorships, a low level of commitment results in only modest success for policy initiatives.

Furthermore, high awareness of PR activities does not inherently translate into policy acceptance. Ejiogu et al. (2024) found that residents in Owerri remained indifferent to government projects despite high exposure to PR strategies, suggesting a profound gap between message delivery and public sentiment. However, Omachi et al. (2024) and Nwafor et al. (2022) argue that proactive engagement, transparency, and the inclusion of traditional community stakeholders (e.g., town unions) are vital for fostering trust and participation. While the extant literature covers diverse sectors and crises, there remains a need to examine the specific intersection of PR strategies and public perception regarding education policy in Taraba State.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the Public Relations Theory of Value, an offshoot of the International Association of Business Communicators (IABC) Excellence Study conducted between the 1970s and 1980s (Grunig & Grunig, 2008). The theory posits that public relations provides intrinsic value by aligning organisational objectives with public interest. This framework advocates public relations as a strategic management function integrated into organisational leadership and decision-making processes rather than merely serving as a publicity tool. Central to this theory is the two-way symmetrical model, which prioritizes mutual understanding and relationship quality over one-way persuasion. While Ki and Hon (2007) found that such dialogue increases stakeholder trust, critics like Holtzhausen (2000) argue that bureaucratic or volatile political environments often force PR into asymmetrical, persuasive roles, particularly where budget constraints or political interference limit genuine engagement.

This study adopts the Excellence Theory to evaluate whether the Taraba State Government utilized PR as a strategic necessity or a mere technical task in promoting its free education policy. By applying these normative benchmarks, the research assesses how the presence (or absence) of strategic integration and symmetrical communication influenced public perception. This theoretical lens is vital for determining if the government's communication efforts met the standards of professional excellence required to foster social mobilization and long-term policy acceptance within the state's unique socio-political landscape.

Research Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods research design, integrating a quantitative survey with qualitative in-depth interviews to capture both the breadth of public perception and the depth of administrative intent. The target population comprises approximately 1.98 million adults in Taraba State, from which a sample of 384 respondents was drawn for the survey, consistent with Krejcie and Morgan's specifications. Using a stratified random sampling technique, Jalingo, Gassol, and Wukari LGAs were selected to represent the state's three senatorial zones, with sample sizes proportionally allocated based on population density. For the qualitative component, 26 key stakeholders including government officials and community leaders were purposively interviewed, reaching data saturation to ensure a comprehensive understanding of institutional PR challenges. Data collection utilized a questionnaire and an interview guide. The research instruments were validated by senior academics and public relations professionals prior to administration to ensure content and face validity. In addition, the questionnaire's reliability was confirmed through the test-retest method, which yielded a Pearson correlation coefficient above 0.75. Quantitative data were processed using SPSS to generate descriptive statistics and cross-tabulations, while qualitative responses were analyzed through Braun and Clarke's inductive thematic analysis framework.

Data Presentation

4.1.1 Quantitative Data

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Items	Responses	n=384	Percentage (%=100)
Gender	Male	204	53.1%
	Female	180	46.9%
Age Range	18 – 25 years	72	18.8%
	26 – 35 years	128	33.3%
	36 – 45 years	110	28.6%
	46 years and above	74	19.3%
Senatorial Zone/LGA	Northern Zone (Jalingo)	154	40.1%
	Central Zone (Gassol)	96	25.0%
	Southern Zone (Wukari)	134	34.9%
Educational Qual.	FSLC	21	5.5%
	SSCE	40	10.4%
	Diploma / NCE	114	29.7%
	First Degree (B.Sc/B.A/HND)	156	40.6%
	Postgraduate Degree	46	12.0%

Primary Occupation	Civil Servant	142	37.0%
	Trader / Business Owner	98	25.5%
	Farmer	84	21.9%
	Student	42	10.6%
	Unemployed	18	4.7%

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Table 1 presents the demographic data of the respondents. The gender distribution was relatively balanced, with males (53.1%) slightly outnumbering females (46.9%). The majority of participants fell within the 26–45 age range (61.9%), representing the primary stakeholder group of parents and guardians most affected by educational reforms. Geographically, respondents were distributed across three senatorial zones: Jalingo (40.1%), Wukari (34.9%), and Gassol (25.0%), ensuring a broad representation of the state's socio-cultural landscape. The respondents demonstrated high literacy levels, with 82.3% possessing tertiary qualifications, including 12.0% with postgraduate degrees. This educational depth suggests the sample was well-equipped to provide informed perspectives on government PR strategies. Occupationally, the sample was diverse, led by civil servants (37.0%) and traders (25.5%), but also including farmers (21.9%) and students (10.6%). This occupational variety ensures that the study captures perceptions from both formal and informal sectors of the Taraba State economy.

Table 2: Respondents Perceived Level of Adoption of PR Strategies by the State Government

S/N	GPR Strategy Items	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Regular press briefings and news releases.	180	144	30	20	10	4.21	0.94	Very High
2	Use of radio jingles and broadcasts.	25	35	44	130	150	2.09	1.14	Very Low
3	Use of traditional and religious leaders.	15	20	60	160	129	2.04	0.96	Very Low
4	Use of social media	32	38	70	124	120	2.28	1.20	Low
5	Workshops and seminars for stakeholders.	10	15	40	159	160	1.83	0.88	Very Low
6	Use of Parent-Teacher Associations (PTA).	12	18	50	144	160	1.90	0.92	Very Low
7	Community forums and town hall meetings.	8	12	34	170	160	1.77	0.81	Very Low
8	Advocacy visits to key community groups.	14	16	40	164	150	1.89	0.90	Very Low
9	Direct facility or school visitations by officials.	20	30	54	140	140	2.10	1.09	Very Low
10	Branded instructional materials and billboards.	18	22	80	134	130	2.11	1.04	Very Low
	Grand Mean Score						2.22	0.99	Low Adoption

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Decision criterion: 3.50 – 5.00=Very High, 3.00 – 3.49=High, 2.00 – 2.50=Low & 1.99-00=Very Low

The data in Table 2 above reveal the dominant GPR strategies used by the Taraba State Government in promoting the free education policy. The result indicate that press briefings and news releases (M=4.21) were the only strategies with a high level of adoption, suggesting a communication architecture heavily centralized around traditional media relations. However, participatory strategies such as PTA engagements (M=1.90), community forums (M=1.77), advocacy visits (M=1.89), and traditional/religious leader channels (M=2.04) all recorded low levels of adoption. The Grand Mean of 2.22 underscores an overall failure to deploy a diversified PR mix. This imbalance indicates a significant communication gap.

Table 3: Respondents’ Perceived Level of Awareness and Understanding of Free Education Policy in Taraba State

S/N	Awareness & Understanding Items	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	M	SD	Remark
1	I am aware that the policy provides for the total cancellation of tuition fees in all public primary and secondary schools.	198	142	14	20	10	4.29	0.94	Very high
2	I am aware that the State Government has implemented a 50% reduction in school fees for all state-owned tertiary institutions.	165	135	34	30	20	4.03	1.05	Very high
3	I understand that the policy strictly forbids school heads from charging hidden or extra-curricular levies.	150	140	44	30	20	3.96	1.02	High
4	I know that the free education policy is specifically for students in public schools and not private institutions.	160	134	40	30	20	4.00	1.04	Very high
5	I am aware that the policy includes the provision of free school uniforms and textbooks for all students.	30	40	54	140	120	2.11	1.08	Low
6	I am aware of the state-sponsored school feeding programme as a key component of this policy.	25	35	50	144	130	2.13	1.06	Low
Grand Mean Score							3.42	1.03	High

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Decision criterion: 3.50 – 5.00=Very High, 3.00 – 3.49=High & 0.00 – 2.99=Low

The findings in Table 3 indicate that respondents awareness and knowledge of the free education policy. While the Grand Mean of 3.42 confirms a generally high level of public awareness, the disparity between fee-related items and provision-related items reveals a critical gap. This suggests that while PR strategies effectively disseminate basic information, they have yet to achieve attitudinal conviction regarding the holistic implementation of the government’s educational initiatives.

Table 4: Public Perception of the Free Education Policy

S/N	Perception Items	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	M	SD	Remark
1	Free Education Policy has improved school enrollment.	135	125	44	50	30	3.74	1.20	Accepted (+)
2	The policy is implemented effectively at all levels.	10	15	40	155	164	1.81	0.88	Rejected (-)
3	The government is genuinely committed to sustaining the policy.	12	14	45	153	160	1.86	0.89	Rejected (-)
4	The free education policy is a mere political gimmick.	185	145	20	19	15	4.21	0.99	Accepted (-)
Grand Mean Score							2.91	0.99	Negative

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

Decision criterion: 3.50 – 5.00 = Positive (+); 3.00 – 3.49 = Neutral (O); 0.00 – 2.99 = Negative (-)

The data in Table 4 reveals a predominantly negative public perception of the free education policy, highlighting a critical gap between information dissemination and institutional credibility. While respondents acknowledge that the policy has improved school enrollment (M=3.74), they remain deeply skeptical of the government's administrative capacity and underlying motives with a Grand Mean of 2.91 suggesting that while government PR strategies have succeeded in generating publicity and highlighting enrollment gains, they have failed to cultivate public trust or attitudinal conviction.

Table 5: Perceived Challenges Undermining Government PR Communication of free Education in Taraba State

S/N	Challenges/Barriers items	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	M	SD	Remark
1	Lack of two-way communication and feedback mechanisms between the government and the public.	180	140	24	20	20	4.15	1.05	Accepted
2	Over-reliance on press briefings and political media rather than community-based channels.	170	145	34	20	15	4.13	0.99	Accepted
3	Perceived inconsistency between government claims and the actual state of school facilities.	165	135	40	24	20	4.04	1.06	Accepted
4	Political interference in the dissemination of policy information.	160	150	30	24	20	4.06	1.02	Accepted
5	Adequate information is provided on the long-term funding and sustainability of the policy.	12	18	60	164	130	2.01	0.89	Rejected
Grand Mean Score							3.68	1.00	Accepted

Decision criterion: 3.50 – 5.00 = Accepted while 0-00-2.59 Negative=Rejected

The findings in Table 5 identify critical barriers that undermine GPR for the free education policy in Taraba State. The most significant challenge is the lack of two-way communication (M=4.15), which confirms that the government's strategy is perceived as a top-down imposition rather than an engaging dialogue. This is compounded by an over-reliance on press briefings (M=4.13), which the public views as a vehicle for political posturing rather than authentic service information. A profound disconnect between PR messaging and the actual condition of school facilities with a Grand Mean of 3.68, the results demonstrate that these systemic PR failures are the primary drivers of the policy's ongoing credibility crisis.

Qualitative Data

The interview responses with 26 key stakeholders including government officials and community leaders yielded five dominant themes:

Overreliance on Traditional Media

Interviews revealed a heavy dependence on mass media. While government officials viewed press briefings as authoritative (Participant 2), school administrators and community leaders described the approach as detached and distant (Participant 9). This corroborates the quantitative findings of high adoption for press releases but low engagement in community forums, indicating a Public Information (One-way) model rather than two-way symmetrical communication.

Tuition-Centric Awareness Gaps

The interviewees revealed that awareness of the policy as a result of GPR is largely limited to fee cancellations. Officials admitted that PR campaigns intentionally prioritised tuition to remove "financial barriers" narrative (Participants 3, 10, 19, 20), leaving supportive components like textbooks and school feeding in a logistical vacuum. Aoso, others reported confusion when still facing out-of-pocket expenses (Participant 25), while principals felt pressured by declarations that outpaced the on-ground reality (Participant 11).

Policy as a Political Gimmick

Participants overwhelmingly associated the PR strategy with administration branding rather than institutionalisation. Officials noted that the policy serves as the flagship brand for the governor (Participant 1), leading stakeholders to suspect the initiative may not outlive the current political cycle (Participant 23). This explains the high survey mean regarding the perception of the policy as a political gimmick.

Weak Feedback and Communication Gap

A significant barrier revealed by the interviewees is the absence of a structured feedback system. The participants reported a lack of formal channels to report grievances (Participant 24), a challenge confirmed by officials who admitted to focusing on telling the story without a system to capture grassroots reactions (Participant 4).

Demand for Participatory Engagement

Participants consistently advocated for a shift toward participatory communication. Suggestions included leveraging Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs), traditional rulers, and religious leaders to build trust (Participants 12 & 24). Government officials also acknowledged the need to move beyond radio toward Stakeholder Workshops and direct facility visitations to foster long-term policy acceptance (Participant 2).

Discussion of Findings

The study first identified that the GPR strategies employed by Taraba State Government to promote its free education policy. The result reveal that the government relies almost exclusively on a centralised, top-down publicity model dominated by press briefings and state-owned broadcasts. This findings align with Eyo and Onyewuchi (2025), who noted that the Press Agency/Publicity Model remains the default for Nigerian public organisations due to rigid bureaucracy. This results in an underdeveloped PR status, as previously observed by Geremew (2017) and Anyijuka (2016), where communication is reduced to mere information dissemination. Theoretically, this contradicts the Theory of Value in Public Relations, which prescribes a participative, Two-Way Symmetrical Model to build trust (Grunig et al., 1992).

The study further found that, while the GPR strategies achieved high awareness regarding tuition cancellation, it simultaneously created a significant knowledge gap concerning supportive components like instructional materials and school feeding. This mirrors Ejiogu et al. (2024), who found that high exposure to government PR does not necessarily translate into a deeper understanding of a project's full scope. Unlike the successful hybrid approaches seen in Indonesia (Kede et al., 2021), Taraba's media-heavy, tuition-centric narrative has diverged from the public's reality. By focusing on political wins while remaining silent on logistical needs such as uniforms and feeding the government failed to adapt its message to the specific values of its audience, a key requirement for effective communication accommodation (Giles, 2016).

Despite high awareness of the policy, the study established that public perception is deeply negative, majority of the people perceived the policy as political gimmick. This finding supports Ejiogu et al. (2024) but departs from Omachi et al. (2024), whose study in Kogi State proved that proactive engagement and transparency foster positive participation. The gimmick label suggests that the government prioritised branding the Governor's agenda over the institutionalisation required for social responsibility (Grunig et al., 1992). By using PR for brand positioning rather than genuine relationship building, the state inadvertently validated public suspicion. It was also found that the primary challenges hindering the GPR strategies in promoting the policy are a feedback vacuum and a disconnect between PR messaging and grassroots reality. These findings support Irawanto et al. (2022) and Ahmed et al. (2024), suggesting that a low level of commitment to PR depth results in minimal impact. The loudness of publicity highlights the silence of feedback channels, violating the Symmetrical Model which requires a two-way flow of information (Grunig et al., 1992).

Conclusion

The study concludes that the Taraba State Government's heavy reliance on one-way media relations strategies (primarily press releases and briefings) for promoting its 2023 free education policy, while achieving high awareness, has proven largely ineffective in building public understanding, trust, and acceptance. This outcome strongly validates the core tenets of Excellence Theory (Grunig & Hunt, 1984) in a volatile Nigerian political context. The findings demonstrate that in environments characterised by low public trust, ethnic diversity, and political cynicism, the one-way communication model falls short, whereas the adoption of two-way symmetrical communication characterised by dialogue, feedback mechanisms, and relationship-building is essential for achieving genuine policy support and institutional credibility.

Recommendations

To enhance GPR of the state and public participation and acceptance of the free education policy, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The government should shift from centralised media broadcasts to school-district committees involving PTA chairmen, traditional rulers, and student representatives to ensure the policy is communicated through trusted local voices.
2. The Ministry of Education should launch a digital dashboard providing real-time, verifiable data on the delivery of school materials to provide visible evidence of implementation.
3. Toll-free lines and WhatsApp bots should be established to allow citizens to report illegalities such as hidden fees or supply shortages directly to the PR department.
4. The government should utilise culturally resonant interpersonal strategies, such as town hall meetings in market squares and palaces, to reach the informal sector effectively.
5. Principals should be trained as frontline PR managers and equipped with communication toolkits to serve as the primary, authoritative source of information for parents.

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